

Complex network science can help children to develop sports that are adapted to them

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How can we guide on selecting the most suitable sports for children? Should we base our choices solely on the child's interests or the expectations of parents? Opting for sports without scientific backing not only consumes more time and resources but can also undermine a child's motivation and enthusiasm. It is essential to offer recommendations based on the child's actual physical abilities and talent.

A Potential Solution: Complex Network Science

Complex network analysis, as an innovative method for assessing variables within a complex dynamic system, has demonstrated its effectiveness in evaluating athletes' performance (Gobatto et al., 2020; Pereira et al., 2018, 2019; Zhang & Fan, 2021). In this network model, each measured parameter is represented as a node, and the relationships between these nodes are depicted as edges. By constructing such a network model, it becomes possible to discern correlations between each parameter and identify distinct network patterns across different sports.

How It Works

The diagram illustrates the application of complex network science in children's sports development.

In the initial layer, three sports options that a child might be interested in or currently engaged in are presented.

Subsequently, a battery of physical performance tests is conducted (as indicated in the middle layer of Figure 1), encompassing elements such as instantaneous power, physical prowess, agility, speed, specialization, endurance, rhythm, responsiveness, spatial awareness, and more.

In the final layer, the assessed physical performance is visualized through a graphical complex network that highlights connections among various parameters.

Following this, based on the results of network analysis, a comparison can be made between the child's performance and that of professional athletes (provided relevant data is obtained in advance).

This enables us to offer recommendations regarding the most suitable sport for the child and to create a customized training program tailored to their needs.

Who Should Be Involved?

Stakeholders in this process include children and their parents, coaches or advisors, and researchers from diverse fields, including sports science, developmental psychology, healthcare and nutrition, neuroscience and human behavior, mathematics and statistics, anthropology, and engineering.

In conclusion, complex network analysis stands as an evidence-based advisory approach that can significantly contribute to the development of children's sports. It is anticipated that this interdisciplinary study will generate increasing interest within the academic community.

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